

Teacher Victimization in Philippine College of Science and Technology

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Abstract:- Anyone can be victims. Victimization may happen either with or without the knowledge or permission of the person to be victimized by the perpetrator. It can occur even when attending school. In line with this, not only are students at risk of being victimized at school, but teachers may also become victims. The objective of this study is to determine teacher victimization in Senior High School in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST). The study used a descriptive survey and data gathered was tabulated and statistically treated using frequency, percentage, and ranking, weighted mean, and one-way ANOVA. As a result, the profile of victimization of senior high school teachers are mostly verbal assault happening in school premises by students and it happened at least once; the factor that contributes to the victimization is their attitude/personality; and the effect of victimization on their wellbeing is less severe in psychological, emotional, and social while there is no impact on the physical being. It was concluded that Senior High School teachers in PhilCST are not exempted from victimization; chances of victimization may depend on the victims' attributes toward their assailant, and the severity of victimization does not cause much impact.

Keywords:- Impact Of Victimization, Senior High School Teachers, Teacher Victimization, Victimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Crimes and criminals are essential in our society (Kalalang, 2011). As the theory proposed by Emile Durkheim, it described that crime is a regular phenomenon supporting his credence that crime works as a social function to support the social norms of a society wherein fact, crime is considered is considered to be occurrences against the norm (JB912, 2012).

In evaluating Durkheim's theory, some realists criticize the impression that crime is both normal and functional, pointing out that crime is a problem for victims and for society itself. With this, there is a need to inform the policy makers-makers in order to prevent the commission of crimes (Hall, n.d.).

In line with this, criminal justice professionals work to minimize crimes and solve crimes and make sure that justice is served. In addition, they also play a vital role in terms of helping the victims of crimes by utilizing approaches

grounded in victimology. Although at some point, criminal justice professionals are searching for new methods to understand the mind of criminals and how to rehabilitate them, they also utilize victimology in order to understand why a victim is being victimized (Hussung, 2017).

Anyone can be a victim of mishaps, diseases, calamities, or social problems like rivalry, discrimination, and other hazards resulting from victims that were harmed because of illegal acts or any misfortune events (Kalalang, 2011).

In addition, victims of crime may be varied by means of gender, age, race, or ethnicity. Victimization may occur to anybody, it might be in a form of an individual or even a group, and a crime itself may happen to a person or property. The effect of crime on the victims, the people around them, or even the community may depend on a variety of factors, but most often, crime victimization has an impact on the emotional, psychological, physical, financial, and social consequences ("Victims & Victimization", n.d.).

Therefore, victimization may happen either with or without the knowledge or permission of the person to be victimized by the perpetrator. Victimization is an asymmetrical relationship that is disruptive and, in many cases, a violation of the law. (Kalalang, 2011).

Nevertheless, people are not always safe from damage or injury while they try to earn a living. Since victimization can happen to anyone or anywhere, victimization can occur even when attending school. Schools should offer a safe environment that is ideal for students and teachers. Despite the fact that schools should be providing a safe environment to encourage active learning, still, it is not exempted from harm or disturbance ("Victimization at School and Work", n.d.). This poses a severe challenge in the community since an alarming number of crimes and security threats may transpire anywhere, anytime, and can happen to anyone (Nolin, et al, 1995).

In line with this, not only are students at risk of being victimized at school, but teachers, administrators, and staff may also become victims. ("Victimization at School and Work", n.d.). Teachers are also targets of victimization. In addition to the concern that violence may take on teachers, those who worry about their security may have a hard time in teaching and might withdraw from the profession due to the risk they are facing (Elliott, Hamburg, and Williams 1998) (DeVoe, et al, 2003).

In Bridgeton, New Jersey, a 2015 incident involving a teacher who is teaching for six years before the attack, named Michelle Andrews snapped her neck backward which caused permanent nerve damage when a 6th grader student in her class struck her in the face when she leaned over to talk her. The student was suspended for a week on grounds of disrespect toward a teacher and not for assault and then returned to Andrews' classroom after the suspension period. With this incident, Andrews asked her principal to permanently remove the student from her classroom but the principal told a sarcastic remark that Andrews should stop whining and deal with the issue. Upon hearing what the principal said, she then decided to take legal action against the student which allegedly resulted in her termination from the said school. Appealing that she was not adequately protected after being injured, she sued the school board and ended up settling for \$197,500. However, the incident left her traumatized and depressed. The impact of that incident caused a trauma leading to fear that she does not know if she will go back to teaching, trusting her administrators, and the possibility of it would happen again. Andrews does not know what to do in facing this victimization whether she fight or flight. The victimization experienced by Andrews is not an isolated incident. According to federal education data, in the 2015-2016 school year, there is 5.8 percent of the nation's 3.8 million teachers were physically attacked by a student and nearly 10 percent were threatened with injury. Some teachers may sue the attacker but on the most part of the teachers who were victimized, victimization among teachers has been an understudied and underpublicized area. According to Dorothy Espelage, a professor of psychology at the University of Florida, teacher victimization is a tough thing to study and nobody wants to talk about that teaching is a dangerous profession and that teachers are at risk when they're in the classroom, however, teachers, whether they differ on subjects, grade levels, or types of schools, are all at risk for violence (Will, 2018).

In addition to the abovementioned victimization in the United States, three among loads of cases of student violence against teachers were reported in the news media on the 2008 school year. In Elgin, Illinois wherein a former student stabbed a teacher in the head, neck, and upper body, blinding her in one eye. In Cleveland, Ohio, a teacher tried to break up a fight and ended up sustaining a spinal injury when students assaulted him. In Lincoln, Arkansas, a teacher's car was set fire during school hours when a student was revenged after being thrown out of class (Honawar, 2008).

In Asia, an incident happened in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia wherein a gunman who was then identified as an Iraqi former teacher opened fire inside a private school's administration, Kingdom School, resulting in the killing of two teachers and one injured. (Mansfield, 2017).

In the Philippines, in Cagayan De Oro, a public-school teacher has been tagged on the flyers as a communist teacher, exploiting minors and molding them to become communists in Camaman-an Elementary School. With the irresponsible, cowardly, and malicious red-tagging of the teacher, the impact resulted in grave danger to her life and family. The teacher

who was victimized and her organization has consistently advanced teachers' rights and welfare with the help of government agencies and sits in the Department of Education grievance desk to cater to issues of teachers and public school personnel (Orias, 2019).

Teachers also experience violent crimes and there is no safe place for teachers. They can be attacked inside the school where they work or even inside their own classroom.

Teachers are the second parent of students in school. They protect the students just like what happened in Zamboanga City. Teacher Lorna Pulalon was stabbed while protecting her students which leads to her death (Reyes, 2010).

Another incident transpired inside the classroom in Antipolo Elementary School in Palanas town in Masbate where a 51-year-old teacher Loida Pagatpat was shot and killed inside her classroom on February 03, 2012 ("Teachers Condemn, 2012).

In addition, another teacher has been victimized in Legaspi City. A 23-year-old elementary public school teacher Mylene Durante, was stabbed to death inside the principal's office of the school where she works. Durante was allowed by the school administration to use the office as her quarters to help her save money since she resides far away from the place she works. The suspect is a grade 8 student in a nearby school which has a possible motive of trying to rape the teacher after investigation finds signs of sexual attack such as the victim's shorts were unzipped (Arguelles, 2018).

Another tragic incident transpired in Bulacan involving a man who eventually turned the gun on himself right after killing a female teacher named Melody Esber inside the classroom where she was holding class in Bocaue, Bulacan (Malipot, 2018).

Also, there are other means where teachers fall to become a victim. Mark Joseph Lontok is in debt of three banks with a total of Php800,000 after an identity thief who successfully granted loans under his name. The suspect had a clear copy of Mark's official government ID after the teacher posted photos of the card publicly on his Facebook account. The suspect superimposes his profile picture on the government-issued ID and created copies, which he used in applying for loans (Techpinas, 2016).

Lastly, not only students can victimize their own teachers. A case happened in Tondo, Manila involving a teacher who has been victimized by her co-teacher. In Antonio Luna Elementary School, Teacher Ruby Gomez, fell victim to Ignacio's impulsive behavior. According to Ms. Gomez, she and Teacher Ignacio got into a little disagreement on their Daily Time Records when Ignacio started belittling and insulting Gomez because of her appearance. After that scenario, Ignacio's husband fumed to the campus and confronted Gomez and then Ignacio started to pull on Gomez's hair. When Gomez tried to fight back, Ignacio then threw a bunch of keys at her, resulting in wounding her head (Failon Ngayon, 2011).

In line with these, there are Non-governmental organizations that make the school safe and assisting the teachers against victimization. The Prudence Foundation is a community investment arm of British life insurer Pru Life UK has one of the main drivers which recognizes that education is key to mitigating danger and contributing to early recovery, and targets to make communities safer, more protected, and more resilient by addressing important matters in education, health, and safety (Malipot, 2019).

Another NGO in the Philippines is the CAMELEON France which is an association of international solidarity, with a mission of apolitical, non-denominational charity and assistance. Its mission is revolving around programs that aim in rebuilding victims, schooling, local development, awareness, and advocacy (Association Cameleon France, n.d.)

Violence against teachers has damaging negative effects on teachers' well-being whether it is physical, emotional, social, or even psychological which is connected to school, job performance, and retention (Moon, et al, 2019).

With the increasing incidents of teacher victimization, it's significant to recognize the factors that allow violence toward teachers to happen in the first place. Some studies reveal that teachers' classroom management skills or some other factors may be linked to student violence against teachers (APA Office of CE in Psychology, 2013).

When looking at school victimization, it is important to note that some teachers are also the targets of violence or criminal behavior. (Victimization at School and Work, n.d.). It has been established that research focusing on teachers is minimal. However, examination of existing research and studies in related areas offers some possible effects of school on teachers. Studies of criminal victimization, trauma exposure and recovery, and teacher stress and burnout indicate a wide range of potential outcomes of exposure to school violence (Buck, 2006).

With this, the researchers find it valuable to determine the profile of victimization of respondents in terms of method of victimization, place of victimization, assailant, and frequency; the factors that led to the victimization; and the degree of impact on the effects of victimization to the respondents. Further, the study aims to develop an action plan to minimize the occurrence of victimization among the respondents of the study. This study will also consider the factors which are helpful in the management of safety and security in institutions of higher learning.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This section discusses the theory and concepts on which the study was anchored. Victimization means being victimized by acts that are illegal or wrongful in nature. Teacher victimization focuses on teachers who were victimized from the start they started teaching.

The study was anchored on the theories and concept of victimization which are discussed in the succeeding passages.

The study was based and anchored on Routine activity theory, from Cohen and Felson (1979), which emphasizes that crime occurs when three elements come together specifically a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of a capable guardian (Purpura, 2019). The theory describes that the routine of activities people contribute in over the course of their day and night lives makes some persons more prone to being regarded as suitable targets by a rationally calculating offender. Routine activities theory relates the outline of offending to the everyday routine of social dealings. Crime is considered normal and is reliant on available chances to offend. If there is a vulnerable target and there is satisfactory compensation, a motivated offender will commit a crime. In terms of suitable targets, the option is subjective by the offender's observation of the target's weakness; the more suitable and easily reached the target, the more likely, a crime will happen. The number of motivated offenders in the populace also affects crime levels. It is then considered that offenders are less likely to do criminal acts if they can reach personal aims through legal means. This implies that criminal impulses can be lessened if offenders observe that there are other means to crime (Myers, 2016).

The Routine activities theory can support the study because there are always motivated offenders since victimology assumes anyone will try to get away with something if they can.

In addition, this study is also anchored on Lifestyle Exposure Theory. This suggests that individuals with demographic profiles were most likely to experience victimization because they are more prone to risky lifestyle exposure. Lifestyles are important because they can add up to the exposure to would-be offenders without effective means to prevent it such as the extent of time spent in public spaces, mostly at night, and time spent among strangers. Hence, it is the exposure to risk and not the lifestyles themselves that produce chances for victimization (Madero, 2018).

The theory can support the study by showing the exposure that can indicate risk to the lifestyle of the teachers that can be a possible target of victimization.

Furthermore, the study is also based on Victim Precipitation Theory. While the abovementioned theories focus on the acts and intentions of the assailant, victim precipitation seeks to understand the interaction between the victim and the offender. Victim precipitation is a controversial theory stating that there are times that victims initiate the engagements which lead to their own harm, injury, or loss.

Under this theory, the victim is viewed as an active element in the crime in which the victim who acts first or the victim provokes the offender to commit the crime. These two ways are the primary components of the victim precipitation theory (McKenna, n.d.).

The theory can support the study in understanding the relationship between the victim and the offender. The teacher as a victim might initiates or provoke the attacker actively or

passively that resulted in the act of victimization. The theory relates to how and why crime transpires.

Further, Batas Pambansa 232 which is also known as the Education Act of 1982, can be served as an anchor of the study. According to Section 11, teachers shall be deemed persons in authority when in the discharge of lawful duties and responsibilities, and shall, therefore, be accorded due respect and protection (ChanRobles, n.d.).

This can also be supported by House Bill No. 58 known as “Teacher Protection Act of 2016” authored principally by Rep. Antonio Tinio. This indicates the protection to teachers and school personnel in charges related to student discipline and classroom management. It is believed that teachers are at the forefront of the delivery of education services to millions of students every day. This dense liability of teachers is intensified by the lack of institutional sustenance in the form of standards and the permissible and effective approaches of instilling discipline; guidance counselors to act as support personnel; and legal aid and representation (Press and Public Affairs Bureau, 2018).

Lastly, the Republic Act 11036 can be an aid also in the study. This law will support to cater the mental health issues of school teachers (Philippine News Agency, 2018). The law grants protection to persons availing health services such as psychiatric, neurologic, and psychosocial by identifying their right to access evidence-based mental health services at all levels of the national health care system free from disgrace and discrimination; their family members, caregivers, or appointed legal representatives by recognizing their right to receive proper psychosocial support and take part in all activities involving the service user; while supporting the mental health professional’s right to safe and supportive environs, and to join in continuous professional development programs (Department of Health, n.d.).

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed at determining teacher victimization in Senior High School in Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST).

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of victimization of respondents in terms of:
 - a. Method of victimization;
 - b. Place of victimization;
 - c. Assailant; and
 - d. Frequency?
2. What factor led to the victimization as perceived by the respondents?
3. What is the degree of impact on the effects of victimization that did the respondents suffered in terms of:
 - a. Physical being;
 - b. Psychological being;
 - c. Emotional being; and
 - d. Social being?

Hypothesis

There is a significant difference in the degree of impact on the effects of victimization experienced by the respondents.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The main concern of the study is to determine teacher victimization at the Philippine College of Science and Technology. The focus of the study is on the Senior High School teachers in the said school. Other teachers in PhilCST will not be included. Further, other institutions were not involved in the study.

Significance of the Study

The study will be beneficial to the following:

1. **School heads and administrators.** They will be aware of the possible victimization of high school teachers in their locality and might develop measures to minimize the incident in their respective jurisdictions.
2. **High school teachers.** This study can help them in dealing with victimization and on how to avoid it.
3. **Law enforcement.** The study will be useful to prevent the commission of crimes in the area.
4. **Researchers.** This will also be beneficial to researchers in conducting future studies on the topic of victimization.

Definition of Terms

Emotional being. This is the feeling wherein the victims may find it difficult to believe they have become a victim of crime. They may even pretend that it did not happen at all. These reactions can last for a few moments or they may be present for months and even years (Canadian Resource Centre for Victims of Crime, 2005). This is the impact of victimization which affects the emotional state of the respondents.

Physical being. This is the impact of victimization wherein the victim experiences a number of physical reactions (Canadian Resource Centre for Victims of Crime, 2005). This is one of the categories on the effects of the victimization of the respondents.

Psychological being. This is the feeling which includes psychological injuries created by crime are often the most difficult to cope with and have long-lasting effects (Canadian Resource Centre for Victims of Crime, 2005). This is the impact of victimization which is indicated in the questionnaire.

Social being. These are social injuries that may be caused by society in the aftermath of the crime. They may include being treated insensitively or not receiving the services and/or information that a victim requires (Canadian Resource Centre for Victims of Crime, 2005). This is one of the categories on the effects of the victimization of the respondents.

Victimization. It is the act of being victimized and aims to be determined in the study among senior high school teachers in PhilCST.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used mixed methods research using a descriptive survey. The method was employed to determine the teacher victimization in Senior High School in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST). The researchers will describe the perception of the respondents on victimization. The researchers used the descriptive survey because it provides a means of standardizing the data collection. After all, the same data is collected from every respondent. The survey research employs applications of the scientific method by critically analyzing and examining the source materials, analyzing and interpreting data, and by arriving at generalization and prediction.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST), a school located in Nalsian, Calasiao, Pangasinan. It is the first College Institution built in the Municipality of Calasiao which is just five kilometers away from Dagupan City proper.

The study included the senior high school teachers in PhilCST. The researchers used the total enumeration and purposive sampling thereafter in the study. The respondents of the study were chosen using purposive sampling determining the teachers who were already victimized from the date they started teaching.

Instrumentation/Sources of Data

A survey questionnaire was used in the study. The questionnaire was composed of three parts. The first part of the questionnaire determines the profile of victimization of respondents in terms of method of victimization, place of victimization, assailant, and frequency. The second part of the questionnaire determines the factor that led to the victimization as perceived by the respondents. Lastly, the third part determines the degree of impact on the effects of victimization of the respondents in terms of physical being, psychological being, emotional being, and social being.

The questionnaire undergone content validity validated by the experts in the academe sector to ensure that the questionnaires are accepted and easily understood by the respondents.

Interviews were also be conducted among selected respondents to supplement the data of the study based on the survey questionnaire they filled out. The method that was used by the researchers in transcribing the interview is the intelligent verbatim transcription since it provides a more readable transcript while staying true to the voice and intended meaning of the respondents. The researchers transcribed the recorded speech into text while editing out the fillers and repetitions that may distract from getting at the content of the interview.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon approval of the title by the Research Director, the researchers prepared request letters to conduct the study signed by the researchers which were addressed to the Principal of Senior High School in PhilCST.

Thereafter, upon the approval of the request letters, the researchers requested for the content validation of the survey questionnaire and asked the Assistant Principal for the complete list of the Senior high School Teachers in PhilCST.

Then, the researchers proceeded with the administration of the questionnaires to the respondents. The researchers personally administered and explained the instructions to the respondents and conducted an interview with selected respondents after answering the survey questionnaires. The researchers personally retrieved the questionnaires. Data gathered were tabulated and statistically treated.

Data Analysis/Treatment of Data

To determine the profile of victimization of respondents, factors that led to the victimization, the frequency, percentage, and ranking were used.

To determine the degree of impacts on the effects that the respondents suffered from victimization, Weighted Mean (WM) was used.

To test the significant difference in the degree of impacts on the effects that the respondents suffered from victimization, one-way ANOVA was used.

III. RESULTS, INTERPRETATION, AND ANALYSIS

This chapter discusses the findings of the study, together with an in-depth analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the distribution of questionnaire that determines the teacher victimization in Senior High School in Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST).

PROFILE OF VICTIMIZATION

This section presents the profile of victimization of respondents in terms of method of victimization, place of victimization, assailant, and frequency of victimization.

Method of Victimization

Data show the respondents perceived the method of victimization that has the highest indicator is 'insult or humiliation' with a frequency of 6 or 50%.

According to NASUWT, a Teacher's Union in the United Kingdom, nearly nine out of 10 teachers said they had received some sort of verbal abuse from pupils in the past year. 86% said they had been sworn at and 46% said they had been verbally threatened (NASUWT, 2019).

In addition, the same incident happened in Buffalo, New York where every teacher says students verbally abuse teachers often. The teachers say they often experience some verbal abuse such as profanity, insulting, and degrading (Lavonas, 2018).

This result can be supported by one of the statements of the respondent who experienced being insulted in his classroom while holding class when suddenly a student is trying to mock the teacher. This is one of the indications that insult or humiliation as part of verbal abuse has been widely experienced in the Senior High School of Philippine College of Science and Technology.

Moreover, the least method of victimization as perceived by the respondents are 'Injury', 'Struggles', and 'Punches' under Physical Assault, 'Theft' and 'Malicious Mischief' under Property Crime, and 'Online Threat' under Cyber Bullying in which the indicators have the same frequency which has a percentage of 9.5%.

This indicates that physical assault, property crimes, and cyberbullying are not common in Senior High School PhilCST.

According to federal education data, in the 2015-2016 school year, there is 5.8 percent of the nation's 3.8 million teachers were physically attacked by a student and nearly 10 percent were threatened with injury.

Place of Victimization

The top indicator with a frequency of 8 or 66.67% is the indicator 'Inside the school premises. Since victimization can happen to anyone or anywhere, victimization can occur even when attending school.

Furthermore, schools should offer a safe environment that is ideal for students and teachers. Despite the fact that schools should be providing a safe environment to encourage active learning, still, it is not exempted from harm or disturbance ("Victimization at School and Work", n.d.).

The least indicator 3 is 'Inside the faculty/teacher's office' with a frequency of 1 or 8.33%. This means that even a school is a safe place, there are still instances that victimization can happen anywhere even if it inside the faculty office.

This poses a severe challenge in the community since an alarming number of crimes and security threats may transpire anywhere, anytime, and can happen to anyone (Nolin, et al, 1995).

In addition, teachers also experience violent crimes and there is no safe place for teachers. They can be attacked inside the school where they work or even inside their own classroom. (Reyes, 2010).

Assailant

Out of 12 respondents, 8 of them were able to identify the assailant and 4 of them did not know the person who attacked them.

This result can support the data gathered on the place of victimization which indicates that if the victimization transpired inside the school campus, the respondents were able

to identify them by the reason that it is familiar to the respondent.

In addition, 4 of the respondents were not able to identify their assailant which also corroborates the data in Table 3 wherein it is indicated that if the incident transpired outside the school, they were not able to identify the assailant because they do not know the person behind the victimization.

Further, the data wherein the assailant was identified by the respondents shows that the top indicators are the 'own student' and 'other students' with a frequency of both 4 and 33.33%. There are a lot of data wherein teachers have been victimized by their own students or other students.

To support this, three among loads of cases of student violence against teachers were reported in the news media on the 2008 school year in the United States where the assailant is their students. In Elgin, Illinois wherein a former student stabbed a teacher in the head, neck, and upper body, blinding her in one eye. In Cleveland, Ohio, a teacher tried to break up a fight and ended up sustaining a spinal injury when students assaulted him. In Lincoln, Arkansas, a teacher's car was set fire during school hours when a student was revenged after being thrown out of class (Honawar, 2008).

In addition, the least indicator is 'co-teachers with a frequency of 3 or 25%. This indicates that not only students can victimize their own teachers but also their own colleagues.

A case happened in Tondo, Manila involving a teacher who has been victimized by her co-teacher. In Antonio Luna Elementary School, Teacher Ruby Gomez, fell victim to Ignacio's impulsive behavior. According to Ms. Gomez, she and Teacher Ignacio got into a little disagreement on their Daily Time Records when Ignacio started belittling and insulting Gomez because of her appearance. After that scenario, Ignacio's husband fumed to the campus and confronted Gomez and then Ignacio started to pull on Gomez's hair. When Gomez tried to fight back, Ignacio then threw a bunch of keys at her, resulting in wounding her head (Failon Ngayon, 2011).

Moreover, an incident happened in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia wherein a gunman who was then identified as an Iraqi former teacher opened fire inside a private school's administration, Kingdom School, resulting in the killing of two teachers and one injured (Mansfield, 2017).

Frequency

The top indicator is 'once' with a frequency of 7 or 58.33%.

According to a study of the American Psychological Association Classroom Violence Directed against Teachers Task Force, 80% of teachers have reported at least one victimization, and 94% were victimized by students.

For the least indicator of frequency which is 'twice', it shows that there are some people who just happen that they are the target of victimization by routine activity theory by chances.

The theory describes that the routine of activities people contribute in over the course of their day and night lives makes some persons more prone to being regarded as suitable targets by a rationally calculating offender where crime is considered normal and is reliant on available chances to offend. (Myers, 2016).

FACTOR LED TO THE VICTIMIZATION

This section presents the factor that led to the victimization as perceived by the respondents in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST).

The top indicator is “Attitude/personality” with a frequency of 5 or 41.67%.

The result can be based on Victim Precipitation Theory which seeks to understand the interaction between the victim and the offender that there are times that victims initiate the engagements because of their attitude or personality which lead to their own harm, injury, or loss.

The results disconfirm the study conducted by APA Office of CE in Psychology, 2013 that reveals that teachers' classroom management skills or some other factors may be linked to student violence against teachers.

Further, factors concerning the antecedents of students' violent behavior were identified in a study by Gottfredson et al. (2005), which is based on a comprehensive examination of predictors of victimization among U.S. teachers with possible factors on teacher victimization that includes student bonding and neighborhood characteristics. The study found that teachers were less likely to be victimized when students perceived there was consistent discipline management such as fairness and clarity of rules (APA Office of CE in Psychology, 2013).

For the least indicator, the indicator ‘Vulnerability’ has been identified and one respondent answered ‘Student is emotionally unstable at the moment’ with a frequency of both 1 and 9.5%.

The result can be supported by the Routine activity theory, from Cohen and Felson (1979) which indicates that if there is a vulnerable target and there is satisfactory compensation, a motivated offender will commit a crime. In terms of suitable targets, the option is subjective by the offender's observation of the target's weakness; the more suitable and easily reached the target, the more likely that a crime will happen (Myers, 2016).

For the indicator “Student is emotionally unstable at the moment”. He then also agreed when the researchers asked for the confirmation of the respondent implying that the factor is not on the part of the respondent but to the assailant which is his student.

The effect of crime on the victims, the people around them, or even the community may depend on a variety of factors, but most often, crime victimization has an impact on

the emotional, psychological, physical, financial, and social consequences.

Violence against teachers has damaging negative effects on teachers' well-being whether it is physical, emotional, social, or even psychological which is connected to school, job performance, and retention (Moon, et al, 2019).

DEGREE OF IMPACT ON THE EFFECTS OF VICTIMIZATION THAT DID THE RESPONDENTS SUFFERED

This section presents the degree of impact on the effects of victimization that did the respondents suffered in terms of physical being, psychological being, emotional being, and social being.

Physical Being

Physical being has an average weighted mean of 1.53 which means Not Severe (NS). This indicates that few victimizations through physical being are being experienced by senior high school teachers in PhilCST.

The result was corroborated by an interview with two male respondents who got involved in physical assault. The respondent mentioned the reason why he perhaps been victimized and mentioned that it has no impact on him. Another interview was conducted with the respondent who got involved in to fight which resulted in physical pain that lasted for days.

Contrary to the result, according to the Schools and Staffing Survey, teachers were asked whether they had been threatened with injury or physically attacked by a student in the previous 12 months. In the school year 1999–2000, 305,000 teachers were victims of threats of injury and 135,000 teachers have been attacked by students that represents the 9% and 4% of high school and elementary teachers respectively (DeVoe, et al, 2003).

Moreover, according to the 2013 Indicators of School Crime and Safety Report, during the 2009–2010 school year, there is approximately 16% of K–12 teachers were physically attacked in schools (Espelage, et al, 2016).

Contrary to the result, in most cases, although violence directed against teachers is rarely discussed because the center of being victimized in schools is focused on students, it has still a big impact.

Psychological Being

Psychological being has an average weighted mean of 1.82 which means LS (Less Severe).

All indicators except one got an average of Less Severe impact. This means that psychological injuries created by crime are often the most difficult to cope with and have long-lasting effects depending on the severity of the impact of victimization.

Emotional being

Data shows that the impact of victimization to the respondents in terms of emotional being is 1.90 which is the highest mean among the other impacts. These reactions can last for a few moments or they may be present for months and even years.

Moreover, according to the 2013 Indicators of School Crime and Safety Report, during the 2009–2010 school year, there is 9% reported student acts of disrespect and 5% reported student verbal abuse for teachers which occurred on a daily or weekly basis (Espelage, et al, 2016).

In Bridgeton, New Jersey, a 2015 incident involving a teacher who was victimized left her traumatized and depressed. The impact of that incident caused a trauma leading to fear that she does not know if she will go back to teaching, trusting her administrators, and the possibility of it would be happening again. Andrews does not know what to do in facing this victimization whether she fight or flight. The victimization experienced by Andrews is not an isolated incident.

Social Being

The social impact of victimization to the respondents and has a 1.80 average weighted mean which means Less Severe. Victims are more likely to isolate their selves to others because they lost trust in the people who might cause the incident.

Although the data resulted to less severe, it is different on the case of Byongook Moon, a professor in the criminal justice department at the University of Texas at San Antonio who received two awards from the National Institute of Justice to research teacher victimization, being attacked by a student can have serious concerns for teachers. The attack had negative impacts on job performance such as teachers can no longer trust the student and views of quitting their teaching career after the victimization (Will, 2018).

Violence against teachers has damaging negative effects on teachers' well-being whether it is physical, emotional, social, or even psychological which is connected to school, job performance, and retention (Moon, et al, 2019).

The effect of crime on the victims, the people around them, or even the community may depend on a variety of factors, but most often, crime victimization has an impact on the emotional, psychological, physical, financial, and social consequences (“Victims & Victimization”, n.d.).

DIFFERENCE ON THE DEGREE OF IMPACT ON THE EFFECTS OF VICTIMIZATION THAT DID THE RESPONDENTS SUFFERED

The difference in the degree of impact on the effects of victimization that did the respondents suffered using one-way ANOVA, if $F > F_{crit}$, then the researchers will reject the null hypothesis. However, since the F is 2.75405805 which is lesser than compared to the F_{crit} value which is 2.99124091 at 0.05 level of significance with 3 and 25 degrees of freedom, then the null hypothesis is accepted therefore there is no

significant difference in the effects of victimization that did the respondents suffered between the beings.

Therefore, the perception made by Senior High School Teachers does not vary along with the effects on the physical being, psychological being, emotional being, and social being. This indicates that respondents have the same experiences as well as observations in the victimization in PhilCST.

This is contrary to the statements made by Ashwin Bhalekar wherein he said that everybody experiences reactions in a different way. Since no one has the same and all have diverse personalities. That there are common reactions that people experience, but the strength and how that emotion is expressed depends on the individual.

IV. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions, and recommendations of the study.

Summary

The objective of this study is to determine teacher victimization in Senior High School in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST). Specifically, the researchers wanted to determine the profile of victimization of respondents, factor led to the victimization of teachers as perceived by the respondents, and the effects that the respondents suffered after the victimization. The study used mixed methods research using a descriptive survey. The method was employed to determine the teacher victimization in Senior High School in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST). The researchers used the total enumeration and purposive sampling thereafter in the study. The respondents of the study were chosen using purposive sampling determining the teachers who were already victimized from the date they started teaching. The data gathered was tabulated and statistically treated using frequency, percentage, and ranking, weighted mean, and one-way ANOVA.

Results

Based on the findings, results formulated on the specific problems are drawn.

1. The profile of victimization of senior high school teachers is mostly verbal assault happening in school premises by students and it happened at least once.
2. The factor that contributes to the victimization of the respondents is their attitude/personality.
3. The effect of victimization on their wellbeing is less severe in psychological, emotional, and social while there is no impact on the physical being.
4. There is a developed action plan to minimize the occurrence of victimization among the respondents in PhilCST.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. Senior High School teachers in the Philippine College of Science and Technology (PhilCST) are not exempted from victimization.
2. Chances of victimization may depend on the attributes of the senior high school teachers toward their assailant.
3. The severity of victimization in Senior High School teachers does not cause much impact.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are offered.

1. Philippine College of Science and Technology should develop techniques and ways in order to prevent teacher victimization.
2. PhilCST should give more emphasis on creating a secure and safe environment to minimize or eliminate teacher victimization.
3. PhilCST should conduct seminars and counselling services in order to overcome the impact of victimization.
4. Other recommendations:
 - a. Researches can be conducted on other teachers not covered in the study.
 - b. Future researchers can use this study as a reference.

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